

These use cases are intended to assist researchers. The instructions in the text are not legally binding. If you have any questions about data protection, copyright, or other legal aspects, make sure to contact the relevant offices at your university.

The use cases were developed collaboratively by the open-science teams at the Basel and Bern University Libraries and the data-protection officer of the University of Basel following a workshop on data protection and the anonymization of qualitative research data. People involved: Silke Bellanger, Christina Besmer, Danielle Kaufmann, Iris Lindenmann, Jennifer Morger, Gero Schreier. [The German version of the use cases](#) was published on zenodo in 2022. In 2024, the use cases were translated into English by Anthony Mahler.

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Reusing Personal Data

Use Case

Nicola Kuoni is preparing a research project on immigration to Switzerland in the 1990s. Among other things, Nicola Kuoni is interested in using interviews with eyewitnesses, which is why Nicola Kuoni is looking for existing data that would be suitable to reuse in the project. A repository contains a dataset that is described in detail and that includes personal data. But it cannot be downloaded directly and is only accessible upon written request and after one signs a use agreement.

Nicola Kuoni wonders how to proceed in this situation and what must be paid attention to when reusing the data.

Why should you reuse data at all? What are the advantages?

If data is available that can answer your research question, then it will ideally not be necessary to collect new data or it will at least not be necessary to collect as much. Even if this is not the case, there can be advantages to reusing data.

In general, you can reuse data:

- to sharpen your own research question or methodology;
- to contextualize your own data;
- to verify your own conclusions;
- to create practice and teaching materials for students or to familiarize yourself with a subject area;
- to develop or test statistical analyses or machine-learning algorithms;
- to make historical comparisons, especially when it is difficult or impossible to find eyewitnesses.

What are the general rules and conditions for reusing personal data?

If you are reusing personal data, the same good practices apply as in all scientific work. When reusing personal data, one must also observe the applicable legal regulations on data protection and, if necessary, obtain additional informed consent. Researchers who want to reuse data should carefully check the origin and creation of the available data and ask the following questions:

- Were the data and the collection of the data sufficiently documented?
- What rights of use are there (licenses, use agreements)?
- Was informed consent obtained and what does it cover?

According to the data-protection legislation, personal data may only be processed for the purpose for which they were collected. Reusing them for another research project generally constitutes a change of purpose. It is then necessary to obtain informed consent again from those concerned (the data subjects) for the

new use, unless the data processing in question falls under so-called [research privilege](#). Legal details must be clarified on a case-by-case basis with experts, for example, with cantonal or university data-protection officers or university legal services.

What are use agreements and when are they important?

Use agreements regulate in detail how data can be reused. They are often employed in cases of sharing or reusing sensitive data that cannot be openly shared or licensed for the sake of data protection. Some specialized [repositories](#) offer standardized workflows and use agreements; others allow you to define your own rules for reusing data. It should be noted, however, that researchers cannot arbitrarily restrict the reuse of research data through use agreements if the organization providing their research funding has restrictions against doing so. [SNSF projects](#) are supposed to share their data as openly as possible; restrictive use agreements are therefore not appropriate for nonsensitive data (such as nonpersonal data or anonymized data) or must be explained to the SNSF.

What does that mean for this case?

Nicola Kuoni writes to the contact address found in the metadata of the dataset, explains the planned research project in a short application, and asks for permission to reuse the data. Permission is granted. Nicola Kuoni can use the dataset together with other materials for developing the new project's research question and methodology. It is possible to contact some of the data subjects again (as specified in the original informed-consent document) to obtain permission for verbatim quotes, which was not previously granted, so that Nicola Kuoni can also cite the quotes in publications.